

Playback experiments highlight the importance of nearest-neighbor distance and social information for nest site selection in the House Martin (*Delichon urbicum*)

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Abstract

Understanding nest site selection is crucial for species conservation. Bird conservation often involves installing nesting aids to increase nest site availability and induce colonization of unoccupied sites. However, prospecting individuals must find nesting aids, which may be facilitated by social information. Here, we investigated the effectiveness of artificial nests and playback in the declining, migratory House Martin *Delichon urbicum*. We selected unoccupied sites with artificial nests along a distance gradient to occupied sites and broadcasted conspecific vocalizations during prospecting times of House Martins in both the post- and the following pre-breeding periods. Visitation and colonization rates increased considerably in proximity to occupied sites. Playback during the post-breeding and pre-breeding periods enhanced visitation rates, while pre-breeding-only and post-breeding-only playback had smaller positive effects. Colonization rate increased exclusively with pre-breeding-only playback. Colonized playback and non-playback sites had similar breeding success, indicating that playback did not create ecological traps by attracting House Martins to suboptimal sites. Hence, broadcasting conspecific vocalizations informs prospecting birds of nest site availability, thereby increasing visitation, and to some degree, colonization of unoccupied House Martin sites. To boost colonization, we recommend installing artificial House Martin nests within approximately 500 m of occupied sites and using playback of conspecific vocalizations.

KEYWORDS

artificial nest, bird conservation, conspecific vocalization, nest site selection, public information, social attraction, social information

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1 | INTRODUCTION

Suitable nest sites represent key resources for breeding birds. Nest site availability and selection therefore show critical effects on bird population dynamics (Martin, 1993). Indeed, not only the loss and deterioration of breeding habitats but also the lack of nest sites or suitable structures for nest building in suitable breeding habitats are causing the decline of many species (Grüebler et al., 2010; Lees et al., 2022; Newton, 1998). Enhancing nest sites and the provision of nesting aids such as artificial nests or nest boxes is thus common in bird conservation to increase nest site availability and induce colonization of unoccupied sites, with the idea of improving breeding density and productivity (Fay et al., 2019; Jones, 2004). Providing additional or improving existing nest sites only contributes to population growth if they are found and colonized, and if successful reproduction occurs. Understanding how individuals find and select nest sites and what measures can promote their colonization is therefore of paramount importance for bird conservation (Valente et al., 2021). Simulated cues of conspecifics have been widely used in birds to attract conspecifics to suitable unoccupied sites, often using playback setups. Although these interventions are likely to benefit target species, the corresponding studies are clearly biased toward colonial breeding seabirds and the American continent (Williams et al., 2021). Furthermore, while most published studies document that conspecific playback increases prospecting rates at nest sites, successful colonization of these unoccupied sites remains ambiguous and is even often not recorded (Ahlering et al., 2010; Valente et al., 2021).

The Western House Martin *Delichon urbicum* (hereafter House Martin) is a declining migratory hirundine species that breeds in colonies of variable sizes (BirdLife International, 2024; Keller et al., 2020). House Martin colonies (i.e., occupied nest sites) consist of spatially concentrated groups of nests, mainly on buildings and bridges in settlements, villages and on individual farms. They are usually well visible and conspicuous. Across Europe, the main reasons for this decline are, on the one hand, the lack of nest building material and suitable breeding sites in increasingly urbanized environments, coupled with the lack of acceptance by homeowners to tolerate the nests and the resulting dirt (Knaus et al., 2018; Allera et al., 2024). On the other hand, the availability of flying insects, on which House Martins feed exclusively (von Glutz Blotzheim, 1985), has been reduced by agricultural intensification and other land-use changes (Seibold et al., 2019). Groups of artificial nests have been widely installed for decades as a conservation measure to counteract this development and compensate for the lack of nest building material and suitable breeding sites (Kettel

et al., 2021; van den Bremer et al., 2024; Willi et al., 2011). Their effectiveness, however, is highly variable and occupation rates of artificial nests vary regionally between 17% and 66% (Allera et al., 2024; Hoffmann & Michler, 2015; Meister & Ehrengreber, 2015; van den Bremer et al., 2024; Willi et al., 2011). The determinants for colonization of artificial nests are largely unknown, both locally and at the landscape scale. Yet, occupation rates were recently reported to be positively associated with the number of artificial nests at the local scale and negatively linked to the proportion of sealed surface at the landscape scale (Allera et al., 2024). Playback of conspecific vocalizations has frequently been applied to increase colonization rates of artificial nests because the highly social House Martin is often assumed to rely on social information for habitat and nest site selection (Marzal et al., 2007; Murgui, 2002; von Glutz Blotzheim, 1985). Although playback is often recommended and used as a conservation measure (Carels, 2015; House Martin Conservation UK & Ireland, 2023; Schwarzenbach et al., 2014), it has never been tested whether playback effectively increases colonization of unoccupied nest sites with artificial nests in House Martins. We thus lack knowledge on whether and under what circumstances playback and other management-related factors increase colonization of unoccupied nest sites, as well as on the underlying mechanism.

Unoccupied nest sites with already installed but unoccupied House Martin artificial nests represent a quasi-experimental setup to test whether the colonization of nest sites depends on characteristics at local and landscape scales. To find nest sites, to assess their quality and to colonize them, individuals may acquire personal information on ecological factors as well as cues on social information (i.e., information gained by individuals through observing the behavior of other individuals; Danchin et al., 2004). House Martins are known to regularly visit nest sites before and after breeding as well as during migration, a behavior that has been interpreted as prospecting potential breeding sites (Reed et al., 1999). Presence and vocalization of conspecifics, as well as their behavior at occupied nest sites are possibly the most reliable source of information while prospecting (Reed et al., 1999). Indeed, various studies have shown that House Martins settle close to their previous breeding site (Hund & Prinzing, 1979; Rheinwald, 1975; Rheinwald & Gutscher, 1969).

To inform House Martin conservation efforts, we investigated the effects of three key factors on House Martin visitation and colonization rates at unoccupied nest sites with artificial nests: (1) playback of conspecific vocalization, (2) distance to the next occupied nest site, and (3) nest availability (i.e., the number of artificial nests). These three factors can be managed to improve the effectiveness of the colonization of artificial nests and

are therefore particularly relevant for management. Finally, we assessed the breeding success of birds attracted to previously unoccupied nest sites.

We performed a playback experiment at 120 nest sites with artificial House Martin nests along a distance gradient to confirmed, occupied House Martin nest sites. Artificial nests had already been installed at these nest sites before our experiment, but they were unoccupied when we started the experiment. We tested the three potential key effects to improve conservation management while controlling for the House Martin occurrence probability at landscape scale (i.e., 1 km²). First, we expected unoccupied nest sites to be visited and colonized more frequently if they are equipped with playback of conspecific vocalizations. Young birds and first-time breeders are the main individuals targeted when using playback for conservation (Ahlering et al., 2010). Since House Martins are migratory birds, they prospect potential nest sites either after fledging or concluding their breeding cycle (i.e., post-breeding) or before their first breeding season in the following year (i.e., pre-breeding). We therefore expected an additive effect of playback during post-breeding and pre-breeding periods, followed by nest sites with post-breeding-only playback and nest sites with pre-breeding-only playback. Second, we predicted visitation and colonization rates at unoccupied nest sites to increase the closer they are to an occupied nest site. Third, we expected unoccupied nest sites to be visited and colonized more frequently with increasing numbers of available artificial nests per nest site.

Our study exemplifies how an experimental approach can optimize conservation planning by identifying management-relevant factors that can facilitate the colonization of unoccupied nest sites. The study develops basic knowledge to provide recommendations about where artificial House Martin nests should be installed and when it is appropriate to apply playback of conspecific vocalizations to attract House Martins and thus maximize existing conservation efforts.

2 | METHODS

2.1 | Study species and study area

The House Martin is a predominantly colonial breeding songbird, preys upon flying insects and often occurs in agricultural but also urban habitats and close to water bodies (Bryant & Turner, 1982). Foraging occurs mainly in close distance around its nest site (on average up to 450 m distance, Bryant & Turner, 1982). Nest sites are conspicuous. They are easily visible on building façades and can also be detected due to the frequent acoustic and

behavioral activity of House Martins (von Glutz Blotzheim, 1985). Nest sites are mostly located on man-made buildings on farms or within settlements and they must be sufficiently covered to protect them from the weather (Bell, 1983, Figure S1). House Martins build natural nests made from mud pellets but also use artificial nests. In many countries, especially in Europe, volunteers and conservationists have been involved for decades in installing large numbers of artificial House Martin nests (tens of thousands in Switzerland alone), which is supported by the Swiss Ornithological Institute (SOI hereafter) and BirdLife in Switzerland (Michler et al., 2015; Willi et al., 2011).

We conducted our study in the Swiss Plateau, northern Switzerland (cantons of Bern, Solothurn, Aargau, Lucerne, and Zurich). This region is characterized by agricultural areas (50%), forests (24%), settlement and urban areas (16%), and unproductive areas (10%, mostly water bodies), at altitudes between 250 and 900 m above sea level. The House Martin occurs in Switzerland from mid-April to early October (Maumary et al., 2007). Most individuals breed twice per season, while a smaller proportion only breeds once (von Glutz Blotzheim, 1985). House Martins breeding in our study area arrive by the end of April and breed from mid-May to September. Egg-laying begins in mid-May, with fledglings leaving the nest around mid-June until the end of June. Second or replacement broods occur regularly in our study area and are weather-dependent. Egg-laying of second broods usually starts at the end of July (von Glutz Blotzheim, 1985). In our study area, about two-thirds of the occupied House Martin nests are artificial nests, and one-third are natural nests (Michler et al., 2015). The most used and commercially available artificial House Martin nests are made of wood-concrete. Differences in size and structure are minimal and therefore have little potential effect on occupancy. Despite still being relatively widespread the House Martin is classified as Near Threatened in Switzerland and is a priority species for the Swiss Species Recovery Programme for Birds (Knaus et al., 2018; Knaus et al., 2021). The Swiss House Martin population has undergone a strong decline at the end of the 20th century (Knaus et al., 2018). Today its distribution is spatially structured, and there are considerable regional differences in the number and size of colonies (Knaus et al., 2018; Michler et al., 2015).

2.2 | Experimental design

We used a stratified-random sampling design consisting of 120 experimental sites, covering an area of approximately 3850 km² (Figure 1). These experimental sites

FIGURE 1 Map of the study area in Northern Switzerland illustrating the locations of the experimental sites. Dot colors represent playback treatments (see legend). National borders are marked with black lines. The inset map shows Switzerland, indicating the study area delimited in red.

were potential breeding or colony sites. They typically consisted of a cluster of artificial nests in varying numbers close to each other and covering a small portion (a few square meters) of a building's façade (see Figure S2). Sites were assigned to four experimental playback treatments stratified by land use, across a distance gradient to the next occupied House Martin site (mean distance: 743 m, range: 43–4243 m) and across elevation (mean altitude: 475 m above sea level, range: 269–890 m). We chose the sample size based on an initial power analysis to estimate the minimum sample size needed for an experiment with four different treatment groups (significance level $\alpha = 0.05$, statistical power $1 - \beta$ with $\beta = 0.2$, and effect size $f = 0.3$; Cohen, 2013; Taborsky, 2010). We used the SOI national database of House Martin nest sites to identify suitable sites. This database includes data on both artificial and natural nests collected systematically and non-systematically by volunteers throughout Switzerland. It was created in 2012 and has been continuously expanded and updated since 2014 (Michler et al., 2015). From this database, we selected all sites meeting the following criteria: (1) Site not occupied by House Martins (controlled before the start of the experiment in summer 2021). (2) At least two artificial nests installed at a site (mean number of artificial nests: 6, range: 2–50). (3) Artificial nests installed correctly

according to Michler et al. (2018) and flyways of House Martins are without obvious obstructions (e.g., tree or neighboring building). (4) Presence of a water body within 500 m of the site, verified with governmental GIS data (Federal Office of Topography, 2023). This resulted in 883 potential sites covering approximately 5000 km², from which we randomly selected sites that were >300 m apart to avoid pseudo-replication by our experimental playback. We then requested permission to conduct the experiment from the residents and the landowners. In case the permission was not granted, we replaced the site with another site with similar land use, distance to the next occupied House Martin site and elevation, resulting in the 120 experimental sites. These experimental sites were on average more than two kilometers away from the nearest neighboring experimental site (mean: 2134 m, range: 300–10,011 m) (Figure 1).

We then randomly assigned them to one of the following four experimental groups: playback after the breeding season in 2021 (post-breeding-only playback), playback immediately before the breeding season in 2022 (pre-breeding-only playback) or both (post-breeding + pre-breeding playback) and a control group without playback (control). We included pre-breeding and post-breeding as two different time periods for the playback experiment because the timing of habitat evaluation by

FIGURE 2 Scheme of the playback experiment, including one control (without playback) and three playback treatment groups.

prospecting individual birds is an important characteristic that may mediate conspecific attraction (Ahlering et al., 2010; Valente et al., 2021). Prospection of first and new breeding sites by House Martins likely occurs both after the breeding season (or after fledging) before departure to migration, and after arrival from migration when the definitive breeding site must be selected. Prospection of fledglings or birds that have concluded their breeding cycle can overlap with breeding between July and September (i.e., during the post-breeding period). Likewise, prospection of birds that have not started breeding can overlap with breeding periods of other individuals between May and June (i.e., during the pre-breeding period).

We excluded one site of the pre-breeding-only playback group from the analyses because the landowner withdrew access to the experimental site during the study. All four experimental groups showed comparable values for (1) the distance to the next occupied House Martin breeding site, (2) the local nest availability (i.e., number of artificial nests), and (3) the proportion of the main land use categories in Switzerland (Federal Office of Topography, 2023; settlement and urban areas, agricultural areas, wooded areas, unproductive areas). Table S1 provides an overview of the environmental variables for each experimental group.

Post-breeding playback lasted from July 15, 2021 to October 30, 2021 and pre-breeding playback from April 1, 2022 to July 31, 2022, respectively (Figure 2). The programmable playback devices (20 × 20 × 15 cm) were

developed at the SOI, equipped with loudspeakers on two opposing sides and powered by a solar panel. We placed them as close to the artificial nests as possible (usually less than 10 m distance) and at least 1.5 m above ground (Figure S2). We used previously recorded House Martin vocalizations from the study area, removed alarm calls and reduced background and interfering noise as much as possible. House Martin vocalizations are not known to be distinguishable between males and females, and no dialects have been described (von Glutz Blotzheim, 1985). The playback devices ran four times a day mainly after sunrise and before sunset, for a total of 6 h a day (see Figure S3 for the complete playback schedule). We adjusted the playback volume so that it mimicked natural conditions and was audible on average up to about 100 m from the experimental sites.

2.3 | Nest monitoring and environmental data

We monitored each experimental site weekly, for at least 20 min per stay between the August 2, 2021 and the September 24, 2021, and from April 11, 2022 to August 11, 2022. Monitoring visits were made from sunrise to sunset (i.e., the activity period of House Martins; von Glutz Blotzheim, 1985), avoiding midday visits and bad weather (e.g., persistent rain, wind speed >4 Beaufort). During each visit, we recorded the presence and number of House Martins at the experimental site, possible

indications of breeding activities at the site, and—in 2022—the number of occupied nests. After each monitoring visit to the experimental sites, we searched for active House Martin nest sites (including nest building and use of natural and artificial nests) on other buildings within a 500 m radius around each site. To accomplish this, we walked along the paths and roads within this radius, searching the buildings by eye and with binoculars. We noted indications of any House Martin nest sites with breeding activities (particularly when feeding) in these radii over both monitoring periods. For each experimental site, we calculated the distance to the next occupied House Martin nest site. We considered all occupied nest sites, including both artificial and natural nests. To estimate these distances as accurately as possible, we completed our data with data from the SOI database. If experimental sites were occupied during the breeding period in 2022, we additionally recorded the breeding success. After the first flight at an age of ca. 26–29 days, fledglings return to their nest and are still fed by their parents for at least a week (von Glutz Blotzheim, 1985). We thus defined breeding success per experimental site as when we observed at least one nestling just prior to fledging (at an age of ca. 25 days) or at least one fledgling at an experimental site throughout the entire monitoring phase in 2022. To do this, we monitored the nests at each experimental site from the outside and also used an endoscopic camera to check the nests at accessible breeding sites for eggs and chicks.

We defined an experimental site as visited (hereafter visitation, binary variable 0 or 1) if at least one House Martin was observed close to the artificial nests, that is, at less than 10 m, during at least one of our monitoring visits throughout the monitoring phase in 2022. Likewise, we considered a site colonized (hereafter colonization, binary variable 0 or 1) if at least one House Martin was seen inside an artificial nest during at least one of our monitoring visits throughout the entire monitoring phase in 2022. Data collection was carried out with QField on mobile tablets and QGIS 3.22 (Opengis, 2022; QGIS Development Team, 2023). Finally, we extracted the modeled occurrence probability of House Martins at a 1×1 km resolution from the Swiss Breeding Bird Atlas 2013–2016 as a proxy for habitat quality at the landscape scale (Strebel, 2018).

2.4 | Statistical analysis

We used binomial generalized linear mixed effect models to analyze the drivers of House Martin visitation and colonization, respectively, with the data from all remaining 119 experimental sites. We fitted them by a logit link

function, implemented with the “stan_glm” function of the “rstanarm” package version 2.21.3 in R studio version 4.1.1. (Goodrich et al., 2022). The two binary response variables used were visitation and colonization. In each model, playback treatment, distance to the next occupied breeding site, local nest availability per experimental site (i.e., the number of artificial nests), and the modeled House Martin occurrence probability at landscape scale were included as explanatory variables. We implemented a full model approach (Korner-Nievergelt et al., 2015). All the explanatory variables were kept in the final model, but a priori defined interactions were excluded. Due to their importance for conservation management, we also tested interactions between playback and the rest of the explanatory variables. We excluded interactions that were not statistically supported ($PP < 0.90$) from our models (Korner-Nievergelt et al., 2015). The municipality of the experimental sites was used as a random effect to control for dependencies due to spatial proximity. All explanatory variables were used in the models after checking for collinearity using Spearman's and Kendall's correlation coefficients (ρ or τ , respectively). Correlation coefficients were in all cases $< |0.14|$ and always had p -values $\geq .05$.

Models were checked for validity using posterior predictive checks (Stan Development Team, 2017). We assessed spatial autocorrelation in the residuals using bubble plots (package “sp”; Pebesma & Bivand, 2005), but did not detect any autocorrelation (see Figure S4). Residual diagnostic evaluation was conducted with the “DHARMA”-package (Hartig, 2022). Inference and predictions were based on simulated Bayesian posterior distributions using 20,000 simulations (4 chains of 10,000 iterations with a burn-in of 5000 each). Additionally, posterior probabilities (PP) were calculated for all model estimates, indicating the probability of the estimates to differ from zero. The effects were considered to have strong certainty if $PP \geq 0.95$, and weak certainty if $0.95 > PP \geq 0.9$. Parameters and derived parameters are given as posterior means with 95% credible intervals (95%-CrI).

Differences in nesting success between nest sites with and without playback, and among all treatments were assessed with two-sided Fisher exact and Pearson's Chi-square tests, respectively.

3 | RESULTS

We detected House Martin visitation at 24 previously unoccupied experimental nest sites in 2022 (20.2% of all experimental sites), 21 of which were equipped with playback. The most visitations occurred at sites with playback broadcasting in the pre-breeding period (including sites

TABLE 1 Visitation and colonization of unoccupied House Martin nest sites divided according to control and playback treatment groups.

	Visitation				Colonization				Sites
	Visited in the post-breeding period	Visited in the post-breeding and pre-breeding periods	Visited in the pre-breeding period	Total	Visited in the post-breeding period	Visited in the post-breeding and the pre-breeding periods	Visited in the pre-breeding periods	Total	
No playback	0	0	3	3	0	0	3	3	30
Post-breeding only	6	2	3	11	0	2	2	4	30
Pre-breeding only	0	0	6	6	0	0	6	6	29
Post-breeding + pre-breeding	3	3	7	13	0	2	2	4	30
Total	9	5	19	33	0	4	13	17	119

TABLE 2 Parameter estimates, 95% Credibility Intervals (CrI) and the corresponding posterior probabilities of the models investigating factors affecting House Martin visitation and colonization at previously unoccupied sites.

Variable	Visitation			Colonization		
	Estimate	95%-CrI	Posterior probability	Estimate	95%-CrI	Posterior probability
Intercept	-1.036	-3.537 to 1.045		-1.582	-3.973 to 0.426	
Distance to next occupied site	-0.003	-0.005 to -0.001	0.99	-0.001	-0.003 to -0.001	0.99
Playback post-breeding-only	0.637	-1.092 to 2.532	0.77	0.351	-1.387 to 2.155	0.66
Playback pre-breeding-only	1.088	-0.556 to 2.891	0.90	1.031	-0.496 to 2.730	0.90
Playback post-breeding + pre-breeding	1.845	0.326-3.699	0.99	0.356	-1.347 to 2.120	0.66
Number of artificial nests	-0.025	-0.169 to 0.078	0.67	-0.007	-0.145 to 0.086	0.55
Modeled occurrence probability	-0.191	-2.943 to 2.856	0.55	-0.069	-2.743 to 2.795	0.52

Note: Factors in bold indicate a likely effect (posterior probability ≥ 0.90). The estimates [95%-CrI] for the random effect (municipality) were 0.28 [0.000; 5.584] in the visitation and 0.14 [0.000; 2.603] in the colonization model, respectively.

with post-breeding + pre-breeding and pre-breeding-only playback, $n = 16$ sites). From all 24 sites visited in 2022, House Martins visited already five in 2021, while they had not visited the other 19 sites in 2021. Nine sites, all of which were equipped with playback, were only visited in 2021, but no longer in 2022. Colonization in 2022 occurred at 17 sites (14.3% of all experimental sites), whereby House Martins had already visited only four sites in the previous year, but not the other 13 sites. Most colonized sites were equipped with playback broadcasting in the pre-breeding period in 2022 ($n = 10$ sites, Table 1). We observed broods at 15 out of the 17 colonized sites (88%), underlining that colonization is a good indicator for breeding. Breeding success was detected at 13 sites (three sites without playback, 10 sites with playback) and—taking into account the small sample size—did not differ between sites with playback and without playback (two-sided Fisher exact test, $p = 1.00$, $n = 15$) nor among all four treatments (Pearson's Chi-square test, $df = 3$, $\chi^2 = 1.8$, $p = .62$, $n = 15$).

We found that, compared to non-playback control sites, combined playback in the post-breeding and the pre-breeding periods strongly (3.5-fold) increased the visitation rates (estimate [95%-CrI]: 1.845 [0.326; 3.699], PP = 0.99, Table 2). Pre-breeding-only playback also had a positive effect (2.3-fold increase), although the statistical support was weaker (estimate [95%-CrI]: 1.088 [-0.556; 2.891], PP = 0.90), whereas post-breeding-only playback had no clear effect on House Martin visitation rates (PP = 0.77). The House Martin visitation rates at previously unoccupied experimental sites strongly decreased with increasing distance from the next occupied site (estimate [95%-CrI]: -0.003 [-0.005; -0.001], PP = 0.99, Figure 3). For example, control sites without

playback had a visitation rate of 0.16 at a 100 m distance to the next occupied site (95%-CrI: [0.04; 0.43]). Sites at ≥ 1025 m distance from the next occupied site had a visitation rate of smaller than 0.1, irrespective of the playback treatment (Figure 3; see Figure S5 for figures with credible intervals over the whole distance and raw data points). The number of artificial nests and the modeled House Martin occurrence probability at landscape scale did not affect the House Martin visitation rate at experimental sites (PP = 0.55 and 0.66, respectively). We found no evidence of spatial autocorrelation (expected Moran's $I = -0.008$, observed Moran's $I = -0.021$, $p = .64$).

Pre-breeding-only playback showed a positive, but weak effect on nest site colonization (estimate [95%-CrI]: 1.031 [-0.496; 2.730], PP = 0.90), whereas the other playback treatments did not affect colonization rates (PP < 0.7 for both treatments, Table 3). Again, the distance to the next occupied site showed a strong negative effect on House Martin colonization (estimate [95%-CrI]: -0.001 [-0.003; -0.001], PP = 0.99; Table 3, Figure 4; see Figure S5 for figures with credible intervals over the whole distance and raw data points). Neither the number of artificial nests nor the modeled House Martin occurrence probability at landscape scale had any effect on House Martin colonization of unoccupied sites (PP = 0.67 and 0.52, respectively). Again, we found no evidence of spatial autocorrelation (expected Moran's $I = -0.008$, observed Moran's $I = -0.019$, $p = .70$).

The interaction between the playback treatment and the distance to the nearest occupied site showed a weak effect on colonization but not on visitation rates (see Table S2). Pre-breeding-only playback increased colonization rates near occupied sites with an interactive effect between the distance to the nearest occupied site and the

FIGURE 3 Visitation rates of previously unoccupied nest sites by House Martins at sites with different playback treatments (playback in post-breeding and pre-breeding periods, pre-breeding-only playback, post-breeding-only playback and no playback) in relation to the distance to the next occupied House Martin nest site. Lines represent the estimated probability for nests to be visited for each playback treatment, shades represent the respective 95% credible intervals (black: Post-breeding + pre-breeding, red: Pre-breeding-only, orange: Post-breeding-only, blue: No playback). Predicted values are shown for mean values of artificial nest availability and habitat suitability.

FIGURE 4 Colonization rates of previously unoccupied nest sites by House Martins at sites with different playback treatments (playback in the post-breeding and pre-breeding periods, pre-breeding-only playback, post-breeding-only playback and no playback) in relation to the distance to the next occupied House Martin nest site. Lines represent the estimated probability for nests to be colonized for each treatment, shades represent the respective 95% credible interval (red: Pre-breeding-only, dashed black: Post-breeding + pre-breeding, orange: Post-breeding-only, blue: No playback). Note that “post-breeding + pre-breeding” and “post-breeding-only” treatments had almost identical estimates and the lines therefore overlap. Predicted values are shown for mean values of artificial nest availability and habitat suitability.

playback treatment, although statistical support remained weak (estimate [95%-CrI]: -0.001 [-0.008 ; 0.001], $PP = 0.92$). Due to large variation and low sample size, we cannot conclude whether the results testing an interactive effect of the playback and the distance to the next occupied House Martin site indicate a potential effect or are the outcome of random variation. The remaining interactions between the playback and the rest of the explanatory variables showed no effects on visitation and colonization and were thus omitted from further analyses.

4 | DISCUSSION

Here we studied the effects of playback of conspecific vocalizations, distance to the next occupied nest site, and nest availability on House Martin visitation and colonization rates at previously unoccupied sites with artificial nests, while controlling for habitat suitability at the landscape scale. Interestingly, covariates that directly related to the presence of breeding conspecifics influenced House Martin visitation and colonization. In contrast, covariates related to nest site (number of artificial nests) and

landscape quality (habitat suitability) apparently did not. The most consistent driver was the distance to the next occupied site, which strongly and negatively affected both visitation and colonization rates at experimental nest sites. Furthermore, we provide the first experimental evidence that playback of conspecific vocalizations boosts House Martin prospecting activity (measured as visits at nest sites) and, to a lesser extent, colonization (Figures 3 and 4, Tables 2).

4.1 | Factors affecting nest site selection

As expected, playbacks of conspecific vocalizations attracted House Martins to unoccupied nest sites with artificial nests. However, contrary to our expectations, only playbacks during both post- and pre-breeding periods, clearly increased visitation rates. Pre-breeding-only playback had a limited effect and post-breeding-only playback had no clear effect on visitation rates. On the other hand, the effect of playbacks on colonization rate was associated with considerably increased uncertainty and colonization rates were overall rather low. Pre-breeding-only playback had a positive, but weak effect on colonization.

The information provided to conspecifics by playback varies depending on its timing, and as a result can affect settlement decisions differently across species, or even age classes within species (Farrell et al., 2012; Nocera et al., 2006; Rushing et al., 2015). On the one hand, vocalizations before breeding can attract birds because the presence of conspecifics can indicate good breeding habitat conditions (Stamps, 2001). On the other hand, vocalizations after breeding in late summer and autumn can influence settlement decisions in the following year because they can represent a cue of reproductive success (Betts et al., 2008). Post-breeding playback surprisingly only led to an increase in House Martin visitation rate in the following year if playback occurred in the pre-breeding period as well, although colony-breeding hirundine species are reported to prospect mainly after breeding (Reed et al., 1999). House Martins are relatively short-lived, first-year breeding, fast-migrating back to their breeding grounds and particularly reliant on food availability (i.e., aerial insects), which largely depends on local and short-term weather conditions (Bryant, 1975; Szép et al., 2017; von Glutz Blotzheim, 1985). They may thus, and especially first-time breeders as target individuals of the playback, benefit rather from information on potential nest sites relevant to the current breeding season without any delay, that is, in the pre-breeding period. In contrast, long-lived colonial bird species, which recruit late into the breeding population, mostly prospect in the

post-breeding period before their first breeding attempt to gather information relevant to the following breeding season (e.g., local reproductive success, Boulinier et al., 1996). We suggest that the unoccupied nest sites were mainly visited and colonized by yearling House Martins because they are by far the most common age class in House Martin populations and lack breeding experience (Hund & Prinzing, 1979, 1985; Rheinwald & Gutscher, 1969). Adult individuals, on the other hand, tend to remain faithful to their breeding site, especially after a successful breeding season (Hund & Prinzing, 1979).

Playback affected visitation and colonization patterns differently. Playback combined in the post-breeding and the pre-breeding periods had the expected additive effect of increasing visitation, while not affecting colonization. We hypothesize that these contrasting patterns rely at least in part on different sources of information or site characteristics that need to be investigated in more detail. Indeed, visits at the experimental sites may represent not only observations of House Martins with prospecting intentions, but also of adult individuals with already established breeding sites or individuals performing other activities (mainly resting during migration; Cramp, 1988; von Glutz Blotzheim, 1985; Szép et al., 2017).

According to our expectations, the distance to the next occupied site had a strong negative effect on House Martin visitation at experimental sites and their colonization. If the next site occupied by House Martins was more than 1 km away, the probabilities of visitation or colonization at an unoccupied site dropped to close to zero—irrespective of the playback treatment (Figures 3 and 4). Hence, prospecting behavior and settlement decisions are strongly affected by the spatial distribution of existing colonies, which may be exacerbated by physical barriers such as forested or heavily urbanized areas. Indeed, when birds prospect and visit occupied nest sites, unoccupied artificial nests close by are more likely to be found and colonized than those that are further away (Václav et al., 2011). This is in line with an eight-year ringing study in Southern Germany, which suggested that more than 90% of juveniles and dispersing adults re-settled in the same village (Rheinwald, 1975). Prospecting individuals may acquire personal information on habitat quality and resources that correlate strongly with the presence of other House Martins, especially in existing colonies and their surroundings (i.e., personal information, Danchin et al., 2004). In addition, they can simultaneously acquire information about the performance of conspecifics at these sites (i.e., social information, Danchin et al., 2004). In both cases, which are impossible to disentangle based on distance measurements only, the accuracy of the information decreases with the distance from the

information source. The distance patterns therefore show that colonization of areas without any occupied nest sites might be much more challenging than colonization of areas between existing breeding sites. Colonization in largely unoccupied areas is only likely to occur in highest quality areas, and in declining populations even such colonization events are unlikely. Furthermore, it suggests that remaining populations in otherwise largely unoccupied regions are crucial for a potential future recolonization process.

Due to the high relevance for conservation management, we have tested for possible interactive effects between playbacks and the other response variables. Interestingly, we can point out a likely interactive effect between pre-breeding-only playback and the distance to the nearest occupied site on colonization rate which shows reduced certainty, most likely due to the small sample size (Table S2). This further underlines the fact that distance plays a central role in nest site selection, which would merit further and more detailed studies.

The number of available artificial nests did not influence House Martin nest site selection behavior, contrary to our expectations and the evidence of Allera et al. (2024). The size of occupied sites may represent an important cue for prospecting colony breeders (Burger, 1988; Serrano & Tella, 2003). Settling in larger populations may indeed have benefits, such as higher survival in Cliff Swallows (*Petrochelidon pyrrhonota*), likely due to increased forage efficiency (Brown & Brown, 1996). The number of available artificial nests, however, seemed to be less important for colonizing a potential nest site, although it can prevent nest site limitation (Newton, 1998). Sites with many artificial nests may still have some conservation value since they can shelter large House Martin groups during migration and prospecting (Szép et al., 2017; authors' personal observation).

Finally, the habitat suitability at the landscape scale had no apparent effect on nest site selection behavior. One possible explanation might be that this factor at the landscape scale is a poor proxy of local density and thus only weakly correlated with the pool of potential colonizers. Alternatively, all experimental sites are of sufficiently good quality and the used proxy for habitat suitability (i.e., the modeled occurrence probability of House Martins in a 1×1 km square grid) is based on characteristics and environmental variables that may not matter at the landscape scale, despite the large variation among experimental sites (Table S1).

In a nutshell, colonization may be the consequence of a multilevel and hierarchical nest site selection process (Mayor et al., 2009), in which information on habitat quality and resources, which correlate strongly with

conspecific presence, or information on conspecific performance seems to be a main determinant for the House Martin. Our results indicate that the spatial management of existing and additional nest sites with artificial nests is a key issue. While our findings inform conservation practice involving colony protection, distance-optimized placement of artificial nest boxes and playback recommendations (see below), further research is needed to improve this management strategy. A better understanding of the habitat requirements could optimize the placement of nest boxes. Additionally, it remains unclear whether the spatial configuration of colonies affects colonization probability. For instance, the distance effect may differ between sites within colonies and sites at the edge.

4.2 | Playback as a conservation tool: General remarks

Playback of conspecific vocalizations represents a rather low-effort, cheap and easy-to-implement conservation tool and has often successfully induced settlement of target birds (Ahlering et al., 2010; Valente et al., 2021). Nevertheless, caution is advised when using playback because it has the potential to discourage individuals from settlement (Quilodrán et al., 2014) or lure target animals into an ecological trap, which can reduce their fitness and even entail a population decline (Hale & Swearer, 2016). Although a standardized fitness assessment of attracted individuals was not feasible in our study, we have some evidence that breeding success did not vary between sites with and without playback. Thus, we have no evidence that our playback experiment caused an ecological trap for the House Martin. Rather, our results suggest that playbacks allowed House Martins to detect unoccupied nest sites, but they based their settlement decision additionally on information about factors that affect fitness not transmitted by the playback (e.g., presence of conspecifics). However, we encourage further research on how playback affects additional dimensions of fitness (i.e., provisioning rates, body condition, survival, life-time reproductive success). Ideally, fitness correlates should be monitored as precisely as possible over the following years after the use of playback, to recognize and counteract a potentially ecological trap. In general, evaluations of playback use on birds are scarce, but there is no evidence yet of deleterious short- or long-term effects on individuals or populations (Watson et al., 2019). However, we advocate the precautionary principle of avoiding playback whenever possible and suggest that playback may be used selectively as a management tool in consultation with conservation specialists and accompanied by monitoring of its effects.

Ultimately, we urge for more experimental studies to verify the usefulness and assess the effectivity of playback treatments under different scenarios and in interaction with environmental characteristics.

The type and volume of broadcasted recording need to be well considered and adapted to the target purpose. In this study, we used locally recorded vocalizations, which are preferable because song variants may have population-specific signatures and dialects that can influence settlement and mate choice (Lewis et al., 2021). We also removed alarm calls due to a potential repelling effect on prospecting and colonization of the experimental nest sites. In fact, alarm calls have been successfully broadcast to deter Cliff Swallows nesting on highway structures (Conklin et al., 2009). Furthermore, we kept the playback volume constant at a relatively low level to avoid conflicts with resident people and neighbors. Finally, anthropogenic noise may have reduced the playback effect by masking birds' acoustic signals (Slabbekoorn & Ripmeester, 2008). However, we detected potential influences such as construction work only at a few sites, and they were also limited in time.

4.3 | Recommendations for House Martin conservation

This study provides experimental evidence for optimizing artificial nests as a conservation measure for House Martins to counteract the lack of nest building material and suitable breeding sites in increasingly urbanized areas (especially in Northern and Central Europe). Yet, the correct installation of the nests and a good choice of location for a nest site are crucial prerequisites. In addition to ideal nest site criteria like the absence of obvious obstruction of the flyways to the nests, being roofed and proximity to foraging sites (Allera et al., 2024; Michler et al., 2018), we recommend installing artificial nests near existing House Martin sites within approx. 500 m distance and using playback of conspecific vocalizations to boost their colonization. Up to this threshold, there is a chance between 20% and 35% of a nest site being colonized if playback is broadcasted in the pre-breeding period. With 1000 m distance and more, the colonization probability drops below 10%. Without playback, a colonization probability of 20% is never reached and the threshold of being colonized with a probability of 10% is already at approx. 350 m. To maximize conservation efforts, it is more efficient to install artificial nests closer to occupied sites. Playback of conspecific vocalizations offers a valuable additional solution to attract House Martins to artificial nests, especially in the pre-breeding period, whereas post-breeding playback has limited

influence. Although the number of artificial nests had no statistically significant influence on colonization, we recommend installing at least two nests initially (Michler et al., 2018; Schwarzenbach et al., 2014; von Hirschheydt, 2012).

The use of playback increases the knowledge of possible nest sites and breeding habitats among prospecting individuals. This is particularly important for House Martins as colony breeders since they otherwise restrict prospecting to occupied sites and their surroundings. Furthermore, it facilitates the establishment of new sites at target locations, as tolerance for nests on buildings has fallen sharply in recent years due to potential problems with feces contamination (Michler et al., 2018). The use of playback to attract House Martins to a new or replacement site is particularly indicated when compensating for the removal of existing nests (van den Bremer et al., 2024). Nevertheless, relying solely on playback is insufficient to counteract the population declines observed in many European countries, especially in Northern and Central Europe. Playback complements main conservation measures such as ensuring high-quality foraging habitat near suitable nest sites, food availability, and nesting material provision near nest sites.

We propose integrating these specific recommendations into a comprehensive spatial House Martin conservation management. An essential first step in maintaining a network of House Martin breeding colonies is to preserve existing colonies. Strengthening this network could then counteract the gradual decline, shrinkage and increasing patchiness of the populations in Northern and Central Europe (Keller et al., 2020; Knaus et al., 2018). Therefore, the planned and targeted placement of artificial nests is a necessary additional step to increase occupancy probability. Subsequently, playback can enhance the visitation and colonization probabilities at new, unoccupied sites. Publicly available inventories, such as those accessed through GIS-based tools, are pivotal in supporting practitioners and accelerating spatial management efforts (Schweizerische Vogelwarte, 2025; <https://webgis.vogelwarte.ch/projects/building-nesters>).

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Matthias Vögeli, Martin U. Grübler and Stephanie P. M. Michler conceived the ideas and designed methodology; Rahel Brühlmann and Matthias Vögeli coordinated fieldwork and collected the data; Rahel Brühlmann, Urs G. Kormann and Matthias Vögeli analyzed the data; Rahel Brühlmann and Matthias Vögeli led the writing of the manuscript. All authors contributed critically to the drafts and gave final approval for publication.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data and code are available on the vogelwarte.ch Open Repository and Archive: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16894186> (Brühlmann et al., 2025).

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

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